

Fluo-8 based assay for SLC24A4 using HEK293 JumpIn SLC24A4 OE cells

PubChem ID: 1794814

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Assay description

Screen Quest™ Fluo-8 NW Calcium Assay Kit provides a homogeneous fluorescence-based assay for detecting the intracellular calcium mobilization, upon activation of SLC24A4. Fluo-8 NW can cross cell membrane, once inside the cell, the lipophilic blocking groups of Fluo-8 AM are cleaved by non-specific cell esterase, resulting in a negatively charged fluorescent dye that stays inside cells. Its fluorescence is greatly enhanced upon binding to calcium (Figure 1).

SLC24A4 is a K^+ -dependent Na^+/Ca_2^+ antiporter, whose activity requires K^+ .

Physiologically, the transporter works extruding the excess of intracellular calcium in exchange with extracellular sodium (forward mode of action), thus contributing to the maintenance of calcium homeostasis.

In particular conditions (high extracellular potassium) it may also work in the opposite direction, increasing intracellular calcium concentration (reverse mode of action).

Figure 1. Principal of a Fluo-8 NW dye assay. The assay measures changes in the intracellular calcium content. Fluo-8 NW can cross cell membrane and, once inside the cell, its fluorescence is greatly enhanced upon calcium binding.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC24A4 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 10'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂. At the same time of seeding cells were induced with 1 µg/mL Doxycycline (not induced control in parallel).

Fluo-8 assay

Medium was removed and cells were incubated 60 minutes at RT in 20 µL/well of Fluo-8 NW dye (1X dye dissolved in K^+ -free Buffer (containing 145 mM Na^+) as indicated in the manufacturer manual) ± 500 µM Ouabain (an inhibitor of Na^+/K^+ ATPase) and plates analysed at FLIPR^{TETRA} reader using a λ_{exc} 470 - 495nm / λ_{em} 515 - 575 nm filter.

To test pharmacology 20 µL/well of substrate KCl (2X in K^+ free/ Na^+ free (NMDG-Cl 145 mM used in place of Na^+ , to induce the reverse mode of the transporter)) were online injected at the plate reader and fluorescence recorded. Different KCl concentrations were tested: 600 mM – 400 mM – 300 mM – 150 mM – 100 mM – 50 mM – 10 mM – 0 mM (8 concentrations, only buffer included).

Data analysis

FLIPR^{TETRA} measurements obtained from different well replicates were analysed by using the Screenworks software (Molecular Devices, Version 3.0.1.4). Absolute Response (RFU) is obtained applying "Subtract Bias on Sample: n" (where n = Timepoint of compound injection) whereas Assay Window Response ($\Delta F/F_0$) is obtained applying "Response over Baseline" correction (where Baseline = Timepoint -1 and -2 before activator injection) and "Background Subtraction". Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC₅₀/IC₅₀ values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 6).

Additional information

Target data

SLC	SLC24A4
Synonyms	Sodium/Potassium/Calcium Exchanger 4, NCKX4
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 24 (Sodium/Potassium/Calcium Exchanger)
UniProt ID	Q8NFF2
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE027X-P (HEK-SLC24A4-WTOE-p5-6)

Assay data

	Compound name (1)	KCl
	PubChem CID	4873
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, #P9541
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 174 mM

Discussion

The Fluo-8 NW assay for SLC24A4 showed a specific and dose-dependent fluorescent signal increase upon injection of KCl. Assay window strongly improves in the presence of Ouabain.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).